

Juxtapapillary Duodenal Diverticulum Type II, A Case of Surgical Treatment

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ABSTRACT

Background: The duodenum represents the second most frequent site of intestinal diverticula after the colon, with approximately 75% occurring in the second portion, typically near the papilla of Vater. Most individuals with a juxtapapillary duodenal diverticulum remain asymptomatic, in which case conservative treatment is recommended. However, if conservative measures are unsuccessful or complications arise, surgical intervention may be considered.

Objective: Conduct a literature review examining the evidence on the most effective treatment strategies for this condition, and compare those findings with the management approach implemented in our unit, based on a case report.

Case report: A 57-year-old female initially diagnosed with choledocholithiasis and treated with ERCP without symptom improvement, who subsequently underwent further evaluation leading to the diagnosis of a type II juxtapapillary duodenal diverticulum and common bile duct stenosis due to extrinsic compression.

Conclusion: Although conservative management remains the standard approach for treating juxtapapillary duodenal diverticula, definitive surgical intervention can be a safe and effective option in carefully selected and individualized cases.

DECLARATION OF CONFLICTING INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

KEYWORDS: Juxtapapillary duodenal diverticulum, surgical treatment, Lemmel syndrome, Roux-en-Y biliary-digestive bypass, hepatojejunostomy.

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INTRODUCTION

The duodenum is the second most frequent site of intestinal diverticula after the colon, with about 75% occurring in its second portion, typically close to the ampulla of Vater. It is estimated to affect 5–10% of the general population, is predominantly acquired, becomes more common with advancing age, and shows no gender predominance.

Duodenal diverticula are classified based on their anatomical position within the duodenal lumen as extraluminal (acquired) or intraluminal (congenital), and also according to their relationship to the ampulla of Vater. Under the Noda classification, they are divided into Type A, in which the major papilla is distant from the diverticulum; Type B, where the papilla lies adjacent to it; Type C, where the papilla is located at its margin; and Type D, where the papilla is situated within the diverticulum. According to the Boix classification, they are categorized as Type I (papilla inside the

diverticulum), Type II (papilla at the edge of the diverticulum), and Type III (papilla close to the diverticulum).

Although this condition is usually asymptomatic, complications develop in approximately 1–5% of cases. Non-pancreatobiliary complications are rare and may include diverticulitis, bleeding, perforation, or fistula formation. Pancreatobiliary complications encompass recurrent choledocholithiasis, cholangitis, acute pancreatitis, and obstructive jaundice in the absence of neoplasms or choledocholithiasis secondary to extrinsic compression referred to as Lemmel's syndrome.

CLINICAL CASE

A 57-year-old woman began experiencing symptoms in January 2022, characterized by colicky epigastric pain, nausea and vomiting that worsened after large meals. She was

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initially treated by a private physician for presumed gastritis, without symptom relief.

In September 2022, she developed intensified right upper quadrant pain radiating to the epigastrium, accompanied by jaundice, dark urine, nausea, and vomiting that had persisted for one month, therefore, it was decided to perform a hepatobiliary ultrasound. The study revealed non-dilated intrahepatic and extrahepatic bile ducts, a 6 mm common bile duct, and a gallbladder containing heterogeneous material consistent with biliary sludge, measuring $79 \times 39 \times 41$ mm, with a wall thickness of 4 mm. An echogenic image measuring 13 mm was identified within the common bile duct. These findings fulfilled one very strong criterion and one strong criterion for choledocholithiasis according to the ASGE guidelines.

She was subsequently referred for ERCP. The procedure identified a type II juxtapapillary duodenal diverticulum with a slightly elongated papilla located at its margin. Dilatation of the intrahepatic and extrahepatic bile ducts was observed, with measurements as follows: left hepatic duct 7 mm, right hepatic duct 8 mm, common hepatic duct 12 mm, proximal common bile duct 9 mm, mid common bile duct 13.5 mm, and distal common bile duct 12.7 mm. Two filling defects measuring 9.5×7.1 mm and 8.3×5.7 mm were detected. A sphincterotomy was performed, and two stones were successfully extracted (Fig 1).

Fig 1. A) Papilla of Vater at the margin of a juxtapapillary duodenal diverticulum. B) Extraction of a choledochal stone. C) Adequate biliary drainage following sphincterotomy.

Following the ERCP, the patient continued to experience colicky abdominal pain in the right hypochondrium radiating to the epigastrium. Therefore, surgical management was decided upon, pre-surgical complementary studies were performed. An esophagogastroduodenal series revealed a duodenum with regular borders and folds of preserved thickness, and a saccular image filled with contrast medium

measuring 23×11 mm (Fig. 2). Magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography (MRCP) showed a 9 mm common bile duct prior to its junction with the duodenum, which appeared pointed due to extrinsic compression secondary to the duodenal diverticulum, with no other relevant findings (Fig. 3).

Fig 2. Esophagogastroduodenal series showing diverticulum of the second portion of the duodenum

Fig 3. Narrowing of the common bile duct at its opening into the duodenum

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Following a thorough analysis of the patient's specific case and through a multidisciplinary evaluation, surgical management was concluded. A retrograde cholecystectomy was carried out through a subcostal Kocher incision. The biliary tract was cannulated to perform an intraoperative cholangiogram (Fig. 4), which showed dilation of the common bile duct with a narrowing at its junction with the duodenum as a result of external compression caused by the

duodenal diverticulum. A Roux-en-Y biliary-enteric reconstruction was then performed, positioning the afferent limb 40 cm from the ligament of Treitz and the efferent limb 60 cm from the ligament of Treitz, performing a side-to-side manual hepaticojejunostomy and a side-to-side mechanical jejunojejunostomy. The procedure was completed without intraoperative complications, and the patient was discharged six days postoperatively without any adverse events.

**Fig 4. A) Transsurgical cholangiography showing dilation of the common bile duct and narrowing at its duodenal orifice
B) Transsurgical cholangiography showing the intrahepatic biliary tract prior to hepatojejunal anastomosis**

DISCUSSION

Most individuals diagnosed with a juxtapapillary duodenal diverticulum remain asymptomatic, and in these cases, conservative management—typically a high-fiber diet—is preferred, as the likelihood of developing symptoms ranges from 1% to 5%. Endoscopic therapy can be beneficial for patients who are not suitable candidates for surgery or to provide symptom relief before an operative intervention. It is also regarded as the first-line approach for those with biliopancreatic complications. In cases of obstructive complications such as cholangitis, jaundice, or pancreatitis, procedures including sphincterotomy, stent placement, and even diverticulectomy have been employed. For patients with diverticulitis or cholangitis, diverticular irrigation combined with antibiotics has been utilized. In the present case, the patient continued to experience frequent abdominal pain despite ERCP and biliary drainage and after excluding alternative diagnoses, the ongoing clinical presentation was attributed to external compression of the extrahepatic bile duct caused by the juxtapapillary duodenal diverticulum and given her favorable clinical status and confirmed diagnosis, definitive surgical management was chosen through a Roux-en-Y biliary-enteric diversion to treat the juxtapapillary duodenal diverticulum.

CONCLUSION

Although approximately 90% of individuals with a duodenal diverticulum remain asymptomatic and are diagnosed

incidentally, both biliary and non-biliary complications may lead to serious or even life-threatening consequences. The condition typically follows an insidious course and is frequently identified at a late stage, increasing the risk of complications that can result in severe morbidity or death, particularly in cases of duodenal perforation.

Considering the potential complications in this patient—such as biliopancreatic stasis and obstruction, ulceration with bleeding, Lemmel syndrome, diverticulitis with possible perforation, and, more rarely, septic thrombophlebitis and portal vein thrombosis—and given the persistence of symptoms despite conservative treatment, definitive surgical management was undertaken to prevent further adverse outcomes.

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